
ASSESSING SANGGUNIANG KABATAAN PROGRAMS: A BASELINE STUDY IN DEVELOPING A COMPREHENSIVE PLAN FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE YOUTH IN CUENCA, BATANGAS

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ABSTRACT

The Sangguniang Kabataan is an essential part of the government to develop the youth in the society and to encourage a meaningful youth participation in different sectors in the community. This study assesses the Sangguniang Kabataan performance in Cuenca, Batangas as it encapsulates the strength and weaknesses of the programs together with the needs, comments, and suggestions of the youth as guided by the National Youth Commission's Nine Centers of Meaningful Youth Participation in line with some selected United Nations Sustainable Developmental Goals through a mixed-method study. The study uses the responses of 250 youth participants from 20 barangays which revealed that their assessments put the programs, projects, and activities of the Sangguniang Kabataan on the lower threshold of the verbal interpretation "Agree" while the qualitative side of the survey revealed the priority needs of the youth. The study suggested a thematic development plan to be used as a framework for the next proposal of the SK officials, namely: Assistance, Developmental, and Social Transformation programs, projects, and activities.

Keywords: Sangguniang Kabataan, developmental framework, youth development, youth participation

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INTRODUCTION

The collective understanding of the youth's active participation in the community-building process with the government has been stained by lots of criticisms. It cannot be denied that there were issues regarding the creation of government posts for the youth. It was mentioned by the UNICEF (2007) that the youth councils were weak in producing legislations, promoting youth development activities, submitting reports, and doing consultation with their youth constituents. This gave rise to critics, doubts, and questions on the effectivity of the Sangguniang Kabataan due to its uselessness as getting the youth involved in community development, corrupt practices of inefficient, ineffective, and non-performing SK officials, becoming a breeding ground for future corrupt officials, and lack of legality of those in the position (National Youth Commission, 2017). These grounds were cited from different studies and comments by those in higher authority in the government and researchers who have made contributions in the development and improvement of the Sangguniang Kabataan. These comments made a profound impact on the view towards the Sangguniang Kabataan which became a challenge to the National Youth Commission to improve the SK and train even better the SK officials in performing their duties as the representatives of the youth in the government.

Looking at the current situation of the operations and visibility of the Sangguniang Kabataan in many localities, it can be gleaned that they are having imbalance focus in developing the youth related to the previous comments given. Sports activities became the focus of the proposal of the SK officials which has become the default activity expected from them, blindly looking at the other needs of the youth in the community and somehow looking at them as icebreakers during the summer break of the students. Though this may not be true to all since some SK officials are implementing other programs that develop and sustain the other aspects of the youth development such as education, health, equality, and civic participation. Albeit they are performing differently depending on their focus, they are guided by the government in planning for activities and programs for the youth in their respective constituency. Thus, it is an advantage for the Sangguniang Kabataan to become more effective by promoting programs, projects, and activities that are beneficial to the youth through assessing the problems in the community and seeking for the needs of their constituents without sacrificing essential elements of promoting camaraderie and enjoying activities.

The presence of the youth in a community shows a better future for the society. Giving importance to their role in our society is an investment in building a stronger and stable active citizenship in a locality and beyond borders. The prioritization of the youth in the community-building efforts of the government gives a remarkable impact in the grassroot government or the *barangays*. In the Philippines, the youth are those who are 15 years of age up to 30 years of age. As part of the community-building process, laws have been passed to recognize the participation of the youth since 1975 through Presidential Decree 684 that identified the role of the youth in community activities where the government gave a way to actively engage the youth in the development efforts of the country (National Youth Commission, 2017). This gave way to the active participation of the youth in nation-building efforts of the government. Thus, the active participation of the youth is expected where nowadays, the youth are trained to engage in civic and politic roles from the *barangay* to the national level. In 1991, RA 7160, also known as Local Government Code of 1991, was enacted to form the Katipunan ng Kabataan to tap and harness the energy, enthusiasm, and idealism of young people aged 15-17 to vote for the Sangguniang Kabataan officials (UNICEF, 2017). The Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) as the local youth council develops over time from memberships, leaderships, names, and participation in the government.

The active participation of the youth gives a revitalizing image in the development of each youth and of the community. The different avenues given to the youth in the decision-making process of the government develops the youth themselves, leading to empowerment, competence, and connection (Collins, Augsburg, & Gecker, 2016). This would mean that the more youth are engaged in the community-building process, the more they are empowered and become actively participating in the socio-political aspect of their life as youths. Even the 1987 Philippine Constitution in Article II, Section 13

recognizes the vital role of the youth in nation-building to encourage their involvement in public and civic affairs. Moreover, this participation of the youth may enhance interest and inclination to engage in community service, political actions, or other public engagements (Augsberger, Collins, & Gecker, 2017). Thus, giving more emphasis on the participation of the youths in the government processes and community-building is hitting two birds in one stone because the community develops alongside with the promotion of the patriotism of the youth.

To counter the negative claims on the active participation of the youth in the government, the National Youth Commission (2021) crafted competencies expected from the Sangguniang Kabataan officials including Local Youth Development Officers (LYDP). These competencies, mentioned as the SK Universe Competency Framework, consists of three parts: core, technical, and leadership competencies. The core competencies expected from the involved persons are adaptability, commitment to serve the Filipino Youth, communicating effectively, and organizational awareness. The technical competencies are divided into two: aptitude and ability consisting of attention to detail, influence and impact, information management, problem analysis and resolution, program monitoring and evaluation, project execution, research aptitude, technical writing, and understanding of youth development; and functional expertise consisting of financial management and budgeting, functional expertise, policy development, and training management. The leadership competencies are also divided into two: enabling competencies which consist of effective decision making and planning for results; and leading competencies which consist of building partnership and alliance for youth advocacy, coaching and mentoring, embracing change, fostering collaboration and consensus for the youth, and strategic thinking. These competencies are set to help the officials function effective while holding the office.

In making the Sangguniang Kabataan more effective, the National Youth Commission (2019) issued Resolution No. 46 Series of 2019 known as A Resolution Approving the Guidelines on Local Youth Development Planning, Comprehensive Barangay Youth Development Planning, and Annual Barangay Youth Investment Programming. The Philippine Youth Development Plan (PYDP) becomes the framework for unified actions pertaining to youth development to address the economic, social, cultural, civil, and political rights of the youth. The PYDP proposed the nine centers for youth participation focusing on: health; education; economic empowerment; social inclusion and equity; peace-building and security; governance; active citizenship; environment; and global mobility. Through this plan, there will be a more comprehensive guideline in planning from the barangay up to the national level of the youth participation in the nation-building process. It can be gleaned that these centers of meaningful youth participation are also aligned with some of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, namely: good health and well-being; quality education; gender equality; decent work and economic growth; industry, innovation, and infrastructure; reduced inequalities; sustainable cities and communities; climate action; peace, justice, and strong institutions; and partnerships for the goals. These goals are part of a plan of action for people, planet, and prosperity as mentioned in the preamble of the October 2015 General Assembly.

This research aims to do a baseline study that will help craft programs, projects, services, and activities that will be beneficial to the community. It also aims to know the strength and weaknesses of the Sangguniang Kabataan using the nine centers of participation of the National Youth Commission. Recommendations will be given to strengthen the proposals for the coming year based on the assessments of the youth in the Municipality of Cuenca. This research specifically aims to answer the following questions that would help the SK officials to draft their plan:

1. How do the respondents assess the SK programs in terms of:
 - 1.1. health;
 - 1.2. education;
 - 1.3. economic empowerment;
 - 1.4. social inclusion and equity;
 - 1.5. peace-building and security;
 - 1.6. governance;
 - 1.7. active citizenship;

- 1.8. environment; and
- 1.9. global mobility?
2. What are the concerns of the youth regarding the programs of the Sangguniang Kabataan?
3. Based on the assessments:
 - 3.1. what plan of action may be proposed to answer the needs of the youth; and
 - 3.2. what are the bases to be focused on by the Sangguniang Kabataan?

By answering the abovementioned research questions, the study will be beneficial to the Sangguniang Kabataan officials in knowing the strength and weakness of the programs being executed and be able to craft programs, projects, services, and activities for the coming year. This will also be beneficial to the youth in the barangay levels to further help them in their multilevel developmental needs. Lastly, the community, both barangay and municipal levels, will benefit from this study since the families and the local government will be able to support the needs of the youth, which may lead to a better partnership with the Sangguniang Kabataan.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study uses mixed-method research employing both qualitative and quantitative approach under a descriptive design which aims to describe individuals, events, or conditions by studying them as they are in nature without any manipulation (Siedlecki, 2020). Hence, this paper aims to describe the effectivity of the Sangguniang Kabataan programs through the selected variables and understanding the needs of the respondents for the same variables.

Research Methodology

A two-part researcher-made questionnaire was used to assess the effectivity of the Sangguniang Kabataan programs using the constructs from the nine Centers of Youth Participation and some of the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The first part of the survey used a 4-point Likert scale to assess the effectivity and the second part will be qualitative questions to know how the Sangguniang Kabataan will be able to help the respondents. Using the weighted mean of the responses in the first part, the results will be given verbal interpretations. The second part of the survey will use thematic analysis to group the answers of the respondents and identify salient points revealed in the survey.

Research Participants

The participants of this study are 250 youth aged 11-30 residing in Cuenca, Batangas, randomly selected through snowball sampling technique, making the respondents answer the survey through Google Forms with the help of other respondents and key persons sharing the link to their friends through social media.

Data Analysis

The data is analyzed using a descriptive approach. It is done by looking over the mean. The interpretation of means was based on the following:

SCALE	Interpretation
1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree
1.76 – 2.50	Disagree
2.51 – 3.75	Agree
3.76 – 4.00	Strongly Agree

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the profile of the respondents, the 250 respondents are composed of 140 female and 110 male participants. It was participated by respondents coming from twenty barangays of the Municipality of Cuenca. On the educational level, majority of the respondents, composing of 88%, came from High School level. The assessments were based on the experience of the respondents on the programs, projects, and activities of the Sangguniang Kabataan based on the Nine Center of Youth Participation in line with selected United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

As assessed by the respondents, the following findings were revealed:

Assessment on the Center of Participation in Terms of Health

Table 1: Assessment on Health

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
There is enough support given in our health situation.	2.84	Agree
There is enough mental health and psychosocial support given.	2.66	Agree
Medicines are provided to the youth in need in our community.	2.55	Agree
There are activities for the youth regarding physical fitness.	2.98	Agree
There are sports activities for the youth community.	3.04	Agree
Composite Mean	2.81	Agree

As shown in Table 1, the study revealed that there are sports activities for the youth community, having a mean of 3.04 which is verbally interpreted as “Agree”. The lowest assessment is on the provision of medicines to those youth in need in the community garnering 2.55 and verbally interpreted as “Agree.” As per the NYC, there should be an increased medical and dental attention given to the youth to counter this problem.

Assessment on the Center of Participation in Terms of Education

Table 2: Assessment on Education

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
There is a place provided to assist us in learning.	2.59	Agree
Support is given for our educational needs.	2.62	Agree
Educational activities are sponsored for the youth.	2.86	Agree
The SK has a direct involvement in our school.	2.61	Agree
There is a free access of computers, printing, and copying for student assistance.	2.41	Disagree
Composite Mean	2.62	Agree

As shown in Table 2, the study revealed that educational activities were sponsored for the youth with the highest mean value of 2.86 and verbally interpreted as “Agree”. On the contrary, free access of computers, printing, and copying for student assistance were assessed as the lowest with the mean value of 2.41 and was verbally interpreted as “Disagree.” The NYC indicated that there should be an effort to improve academic performance and increase functional literacy rate of the students in this accessible, developmental, quality, and relevant formal, non-formal, and informal lifelong learning in this technological age to increase traditional and new media literacy.

Assessment on the Center of Participation in Terms of Economic Empowerment

Table 3: Assessment on Economic Empowerment

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
There are entrepreneurial activities provided for us to learn.	2.66	Agree
Activities to help youth employment is provided.	2.47	Disagree
Financial literacy programs are given in our community for the youth.	2.79	Agree
Skills training is provided for the youth such as free TESDA trainings.	2.62	Agree
There are livelihood projects for the youth and by the youth.	2.66	Agree
Composite Mean	2.64	Agree

As shown in Table 3, financial literacy program given to their community got the highest mean value of 2.79 verbally interpreted as “Agree” in contrast with the provision of activities to help youth employment which got a mean of 2.47 and was verbally interpreted as “Disagree”. NYC aims to promote youth participation in entrepreneurial activities and optimize youth participation in the labor force by decreasing unemployment, underemployment, and jobs mismatch.

Assessment on the Center of Participation in Terms of Social Inclusion and Equity

Table 4: Assessment on Social Inclusion and Equity

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Youth with disabilities are supported.	3.03	Agree
LGBTQ+ are supported in our community.	3.06	Agree
There are equal opportunities given to all genders in youth activities.	2.76	Agree
Gender sensitivity seminars are held in our community.	2.79	Agree
There are seminars/forum for the youth empowerment in our community.	2.84	Agree
Composite Mean	2.90	Agree

As shown in Table 4, the respondents assessed that the LGBTQ+ are supported in the community which got the highest mean value of 3.06 verbally interpreted as “Agree”. Despite this, the study still revealed that the item which got the lowest assessment is that there are equal opportunities given to all genders in youth activities with a mean value of 2.79 and was verbally interpreted as “Agree.” The NYC proposed that there is a need to strengthen equal and equitable participation across genders through increased awareness among youth and the community about different sexual orientation and gender identity to help promote equal opportunities in providing activities.

Assessment on the Center of Participation in Terms of Peace-Building and Security

Table 5: Assessment on Peace-Building and Security

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Our youth community have peace and order.	3.12	Agree
There are programs to support anti-drug campaigns for the youth.	2.96	Agree
There are programs for youth in conflict with the law.	2.60	Agree
Recognition is given to outstanding youth in the community.	2.74	Agree
Abuse and protection awareness program is done in our community.	3.02	Agree
Composite Mean	2.89	Agree

As shown in Table 5, having peace and order in the youth community got the highest mean value of 3.12 which was verbally interpreted as “Agree”. The assessments of the respondents showed that having programs for youth in conflict with the law got the lowest mean value of 2.60 which was verbally interpreted as “Agree”. The NYC promotes the decrease in number of youth offenders, delinquent youth, and youth in conflict with the law through promotion of human security through conflict prevention and management initiatives.

Assessment on the Center of Participation in Terms of Governance

Table 6: Assessment on Governance

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The presence of the Sangguniang Kabataan is felt in our community.	2.76	Agree
The SK is actively engaging with the youth in our community.	2.65	Agree
The youth are trained to be leaders.	2.78	Agree
The SK are capable of leading and representing the youth in our community.	2.61	Agree
There is transparency in the projects and programs of the SK.	2.59	Agree
Composite Mean	2.68	Agree

As shown in Table 6, the respondents assessed that the youth are trained to be leaders with the mean value of 2.78 verbally interpreted as “Agree”. Meanwhile, the presence of transparency in the projects and programs of the Sangguniang Kabataan got the lowest mean of 2.59 and was verbally interpreted as “Agree.” The NYC aims to promote youth participation in government and bureaucracy by increasing involvement in Local Youth Development Councils which will lead to better understanding of the mechanisms of transparency.

Assessment on the Center of Participation in Terms of Active Citizenship

Table 7: Assessment on Active Citizenship

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The youth are encouraged to join community building projects.	2.84	Agree
The youth are informed of their rights as citizens.	3.02	Agree
The youth are trained to be leaders.	2.82	Agree
The youth in our community is heard.	2.58	Agree
The youth are promoting culture and arts.	2.65	Agree
Composite Mean	2.78	Agree

As shown in Table 7, being informed of their rights as citizens got the highest mean value for active citizenship with a mean value of 3.02 and was verbally interpreted as “Agree”. In the contrary, the respondents’ assessment on being heard appeared to be the lowest with the mean of 2.58 which is still verbally interpreted as “Agree.” The NYC aims to inculcate volunteerism through community engagement and develop the traits of social awareness and responsibility among the youth.

Assessment on the Center of Participation in Terms of Environment

Table 8: Assessment on Environment

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
There are environmental project involving the youth in our community.	2.88	Agree
Clean-up drives are initiated by the youth.	2.95	Agree
Seminars and Forum regarding environmental protection is provided in our community.	2.52	Agree
The youth are trained for disaster preparedness to help the community.	2.58	Agree
There is a green space in our community for the youth to develop.	2.92	Agree
Composite Mean	2.77	Agree

As shown in Table 8, the respondents assessed that there are clean-up drives initiated by the youth in their community with a mean value of 2.95 verbally interpreted as “Agree”. Consequently, provision of seminars and forum regarding environmental protection got the lowest assessment with a mean value of 2.52, verbally interpreted as “Agree.” The NYC proposed that there should be environment-friendly practices among the youth and strengthening of youth participation in environmental activities.

Assessment on the Center of Participation in Terms of Global Mobility

Table 9: Assessment on Global Mobility

Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Youth professionals are supported in practicing the profession.	2.72	Agree
There are artistic and scientific program development for the youth.	2.57	Agree
Youth exchange of ideas are supported across barangays.	2.67	Agree
Talented youth are supported for local, national, and international competitions.	2.98	Agree
The youth are supported for their advocacies and volunteering works.	2.68	Agree
Composite Mean	2.72	Agree

As shown in Table 9, the respondents assessed that talented youth are supported for local, national, and international activities with high regard, having a mean value of 2.98 and was verbally interpreted as “Agree”. On the contrary, the one which got the lowest mean of 2.57, verbally interpreted “Agree” pertains

to the promotion of artistic and scientific program development for the youth. The NYC have sought to promote participation in cross-border exchanges by increasing the number of artistic and scientific exchanges through a balanced and mutually beneficial activities.

The assessments of the respondents on the programs, projects, and activities of the Sangguniang Kabataan based on the nine Centers of the Youth Participation and selected United Nations Sustainable Development Goals revealed that most of the respondents agreed that there is the presence of the mentioned activities in their community. Though almost all of the respondents agreed, it is not clear whether the assessment they did was done by the Sangguniang Kabataan or by other sectors of the society. None of the items in the inventory was assessed as “Strongly Agree” since there are different sentiments taken when they were assessed. Though the items were assessed as “Agree,” majority were on the lower threshold due to the gaps on the assessment of the individual respondents. Two items were assessed as “Disagree” by the respondents on education and Economic Empowerment which can be noted as something that the respondents have not normally seen or experienced in their community.

Needs-based Assessment under the Nine Centers of Youth Participation

Though there are several factors considered while answering the quantitative part of the survey, the qualitative part of the survey revealed the main themes of the concerns of the youth respondents which helped identify the needs of the youth in their community. Table 10 shows how the youth respondents mentioned their needs in terms of each center of youth participation as a suggestion for future programs.

Table 10: Qualitative Responses on the Center of Youth Participation

Center of Youth Participation	Concerns
Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ...free check-ups for the youth ...health and wellness activities such as Zumba ...mental health awareness and psychological assistance ...free medicines for the youth ...exploration of other sports ...seminars on health and safe sex
Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ...educational assistance ...library hub/space for learning in barangays ...free access to internet, printing, and copying ...collaboration with schools on activities of the SK ...free TESDA and skills training for youth ...programs for out-of-school youth ...academic competitions related to culture and arts ...recognize youth models for education
Economic Empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ...financial literacy program ...internship programs in the municipality ...job application assistance ...skills training for better employability ...entrepreneurial opportunities
Social inclusion and Equity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ...equal opportunities for all identities in the activities ...assistance to Differently-Abled Youth (DAP) youth
Peace-Building and Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ...include more projects for the order and safety in the community ...programs for youth in conflict of the law ...rehabilitation programs for youth offenders
Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ...transparency in the project expenses ...trainings for all the youth to prepare for SK elections ...consultation with all the youth
Active Citizenship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ...support the advocacies of the youth ...promote cultural activities ...involve youth in community projects
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ...activities for environmental care ...seminars on preserving the environment ...waste management
Global Mobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ...increase youth partnership in different sectors ...support to the projects of the youth

The qualitative responses of the participants revealed the needs and suggestions for the betterment of the youth in the community. The researcher summarized these responses to identify easily the points to consider in this study. Thus, the variables considering the nine center of youth participation together with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals have been seen as effective themes on the overall needs and suggestions of the youth in the Municipality of Cuenca.

CONCLUSION

The results have shown that almost all of the factors assessed in this study were agreeable for the respondents though there are some underlying factors that need to be considered. The activities and programs assessed were understood by the respondents as something done by different sectors, not just by the Sangguniang Kabataan. The qualitative answers of the respondents may have given a clue since it was clearly stated that they wanted the Sangguniang Kabataan to make do their comments and suggestions that might be in contrary with some of the results in the quantitative assessments. Though there is positive feedback on the assessments on the nine center of youth participation that are also themed with some of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, it cannot be denied that the mean values were positioned on the lower threshold of the verbal interpretation "Agree." With this, the study may claim that there is still a close to "Disagree" interpretation that may call for attention because it suggests that many were still not satisfied by the programs and activities done in and for the youth community.

The results may also give a resonance to the results of the study done by UNICEF (2007) that the youth want and deserve to have a voice in the government. Through the quantitative analysis on the needs of the respondents, we have seen how they resonate with UNICEF's findings on the common issues that the youth wanted to focus on: health, education, and employment. The three centers of youth participation where the respondents gave much attention were health, education, and economic empowerment that can be gleaned as the top priorities that the youth wanted to be noticed and prioritized by the government, much more by the Sangguniang Kabataan.

This study may have shown various aspects of the strength and weakness of the Sangguniang Kabataan as participated by 250 youth respondents from the twenty barangays of the Municipality of Cuenca based on the nine centers of youth participation especially on health, education, and economic empowerment. There is a need to reflect on the role of the Sangguniang Kabataan officials to diversify more their programs, projects, and activities to fully respond to the needs of their youth constituents, especially on education and economic empowerment which got the lowest assessment.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the assessments and on the comments and suggestions given by the respondents of the study, the researcher was able to thematize the needs of the youth sector in the Municipality of Cuenca. A three-part developmental programs, projects, and activities must be understood in this concept. Since the Sangguniang Kabataan, as a governing body, is aimed at developing and representing the youth toward its role of the youth in nation-building (National Youth Commission, 2017).

The developmental themes given by this study as a framework towards the planning of the Sangguniang Kabataan's programs, projects, and activities may be understood as: Assistance, Developmental, and Social Transformation. Assistance refers to the one-time, may it be short-term or long-term, projects that answer the needs of the youth that may be constituted of dole-outs and support to be received by the youth from the SK. Developmental refers to the programs that sustain the life-long learning of the youth in a different aspects of the youth that may enhance their knowledge and skills which may give impact to their personal and professional development. Social Transformation refers to the programs and activities by developing the social, political, and environmental sensitivity of the youth that will give an impact to the lives of the youth individually and socially in various aspects.

Basing on the assessments, comments, suggestions, and the different literatures in this study, the researcher proposed a framework towards a systematic understanding of the programs, projects, and

activities that may be considered for the crafting of plans for the coming years as presented on the table below.

Table 11: Framework for Crafting SK Programs, Projects, and Activities

Themes	Programs/Projects/Activities
Assistance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Free medical and dental check-ups 2. Educational assistance (school supplies or financial/scholarship) 3. Free access to internet, printing, and copying 4. Aid for DAP youth 5. Recognition of outstanding youth in the community
Developmental	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Health and Sex Education/Seminars 2. Mental health awareness and psychological support 3. Financial literacy seminars 4. Fitness programs 5. Different sports activities for all gender identities 6. TESDA and skills trainings 7. Academic competitions and programs related to culture and arts 8. Internships and summer jobs for the youth 9. Entrepreneurial initiatives for the youth 10. Programs for Out-of-school youth
Social Transformation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inclusivity awareness to respect all gender identities 2. Library hub/space for learning 3. Collaboration with schools regarding developmental projects 4. Programs and rehabilitations for youth in conflict with the law 5. Promotion of different advocacies 6. Consultation with the youth before crafting and implementing resolutions and activities 7. Promotion and rekindling cultural heritage 8. Green Programs for the environment 9. Disaster preparedness trainings for youth mobilization 10. Support to the projects of the youth organizations outside Sangguniang Kabataan 11. Partnership with different sectors for the inclusion of the youth in the nation-building

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